

Between fasting and religious suicide: A data-oriented reconsideration of the practice of endura in medieval heterodox Christianity

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Abstract

This article offers a systematic survey of evidence from medieval inquisition records concerning the controversial practice of endura, a strict form of fasting practised in a heterodox Christian milieu in southwestern France in the late thirteenth and early fourteenth centuries. Endura usually followed a form of adult baptism by the laying on of hands and often resulted in death. Some have considered endura a form of religious suicide. In this study, we use a comprehensive dataset of real-life endura cases to shed light on the geographical spread, diet, duration, and outcome of the practice, as well as on the patterns in the sociodemographic characteristics and health states of those engaging in it, and on the terminology, motivations and attitudes mentioned in the reports. We pay attention to variation, especially in motivation and diet, stress the importance of instructions and social pressure in addition to that of eschatological belief, and suggest an ultimate ambiguity of this cultural practice, which a comprehensive interpretation should aim at highlighting rather than erasing.

Keywords: endura; voluntary death; suicide; self-harming behaviour; asceticism; Cathars

Introduction

In anthropology and history, few practices have posed such intriguing interpretive challenges as religiously-motivated suicides. They constitute an interesting phenomenon in and of itself (Lewis and Cusack 2014), especially given that research has consistently shown religious affiliation to be a factor decreasing the likelihood of suicidal behaviour (Masaryk 1970; Lester 1997; Saiz et al. 2021). In addition, such suicides raise urgent theoretical questions: What is the agency of those committing them? Are they to be framed as victims, or rather as active perpetrators (Major 2006)? What are the roles of values, beliefs (Folk 2018; Willerslev 2009), sociodemographic factors, circumstances, and social pressures in motivating such acts? Are less active forms of self-harming behaviour, such as the choice to stop eating and drinking, to be considered suicide at all (Maes 2023)? Even singular occurrences of suicide by members a religious community under pressing circumstances – sometimes with the active killing of unarmed or less willing members – present interpretive challenges, with examples such as the mass suicide of the Jewish defenders of the Masada fortress in 73 CE (Paine 1994) and the Jonestown tragedy in 1978 (Smith 1988; Stausberg et al. 2024). Even more controversial, however, are instances of suicidal behaviour in a religious context whose repeated, and in that sense institutionalized, nature makes them an actual cultural practice. Besides the well-studied example of the self-immolation of widows on their husband's funeral pyre (*sati*) in India (Weinberger-Thomas 1999; Barbagli 2015, 192–219) and suicide by starvation (*sallekhanā*) in Jainism (Skoog 2003) and some other traditions of the subcontinent (Olivelle 2011), there is a much less known but all the more intriguing example from the history of Christianity: the practice of *endura*, strict fasting usually leading to death, documented in fine detail from the late thirteenth and early fourteenth centuries in the heterodox Christian milieu commonly known as 'Catharism'.

While the concepts of 'Cathars' and 'Catharism' have been subject to considerable controversy (Zanella 1986; Zerner 2001; Pegg 2001; 2016; Théry-Astruc 2016; Biller 2016; Sennis 2016; Biget et al. 2020), in this study we do not aim to enter this discussion. We are interested in *endura* as a lower-level practice – variable, as we will show, but nonetheless identifiable in the sources in its general outline – rather than in making strong claims about the unity or diversity, centralization or decentralization of the religious milieu in which it appeared.

The Occitan word *endura* means ‘fasting’. It was used to describe the practice in several testimonies in front of the inquisition, and is explicitly reported as being used by the dissident Christians themselves (Palès-Gobilliard 2002a, 1:310). The practice usually followed the initiation rite often called *consolament* in the sources, a laying on of hands with the recitation of liturgical formulae, which combined elements of Christian baptism and monastic profession. *Endura* is often vividly described in records of depositions in front of inquisitors of heresy, such as in the testimony of a certain Bruna Porcelli in front of the bishop Jacques Fournier, describing the death of a certain elderly woman called Na Roqua:

[T]hey told her to give her no more food or drink, because it must not be done. (...) She wanted to give her some salted pork broth, but they did not succeed in forcing her mouth open. Even when they wanted to open her mouth to give her something to drink, she was holding her mouth shut all the more tightly. She stayed like this for two days and nights, and the third night near dawn she died. (Duvernoy 1965a, 1:388)

Various attempts have been made at interpreting the Cathar *endura*, which range from its portrayal as religious suicide motivated by theological dualism and the desire to leave this corrupted world all the way up to more psychological interpretations which use evidence from inquisition records to point out the often pressing conditions under which people undertook *endura*. We might delve even deeper into psychological interpretation and speculate, in cases similar to the one cited above, about a hypothetical feeling of resignation on the part of very old and sick people, who were already about to die. To those, taking food or drink could even have caused more suffering than relief. This could make at least some of the documented *enduras* – as has indeed been argued (Tsiamis, Tounta, and Poulakou-Rebelakou 2016) – a medieval prefiguration of euthanasia.

So far, no attempt has been made to collect the complete structured data on all real-life cases of *endura* documented in inquisition trial records and to systematically survey the patterns in the evidence. This article argues that such data-oriented reconsideration is a precondition for a reliable and balanced interpretation. Our objective was to collect and use such a dataset to quantify and systematically trace the geography of *endura*, the diversity of the instructed and actually followed diet, the known sociodemographic characteristics and circumstances of those who entered *endura*, as well as the terminology used and motivations for *endura* reported in the sources. This new systematic and data-oriented perspective should help clearly

delimit the space in which the interpretation of this controversial practice should be situated.

Endura in previous scholarship

Endura made its first appearance in the historiography of religious dissidence in the seventeenth century. Philipp van Limborch recorded several cases and came up with a minimal definition, according to which, after receiving consolament, some ill persons were ordered to stop eating, and some of them even actively accelerated their death (Limborch 1692, 35). Later, in the mid-nineteenth century, Charles Schmidt was the first to argue that the supreme function of endura was to prevent the loss of salvation believed to be ensured by consolament. Schmidt thus initiated an emic and empathic line of interpretation. He also underlined that endura was a practice for specific circumstances of illness or a desperate situation rather than a universal rule, and while recognizing also cases of more direct self-harming behaviour, he never assimilated endura with them (Schmidt 1849, 1:102–3). By contrast, Charles Molinier, a few decades later, interpreted endura as suicide and a sign of the purported fanaticism and decadence of late Catharism. He sought the motivation to endura in dualistic beliefs, which inspired contempt for the material world and the choice of death rather than putting one's prospects of salvation in jeopardy (Molinier 1881).

Arno Borst provided, in his major 1953 monograph on Catharism, a significant reinterpretation of endura as fasting, and derived its harshness from the fact that it was meant as a substitute for the fasting involved in the usual preparation for consolament, here condensed into a shorter period by necessity (Borst 1953, 197). Borst thus pioneered the disentangling of endura from the dark connotations of religious suicide, placing it closer to mainstream Christian asceticism. In this, he was followed by Jean Duvernoy, who claimed that endura 'is not destined to "speed up death"', and 'does not constitute a special ritual, but a normal consequence of consolament' (Duvernoy 1965a, 1:236, n. 93), and was 'certainly not an institution' (Duvernoy 1976, 170). Duvernoy introduced a contextual line of interpretation of the practice, stressing that the last dissident ministers risked their lives conferring consolament to their dying supporters while being hunted by the inquisitors and struggling with their supporters' breach of the alimentary rules just after they left (Duvernoy 1976, 168–69). Anne Brenon takes Duvernoy's argument even further,

interpreting endura as simply following a condensed form of the monastic rules of life prescribed for the Good Christians who received the consolament, and more in the hope of living the Good Christian life in the event of recovery than accelerating death (Brenon 1992, 330–31).

While this contextualizing and ‘apologetic’ line of interpretation can probably be considered the current mainstream, the image of endura as suicide, even religious or ritual suicide motivated by anti-worldly beliefs, has also made its way into modern historiography. Thus, Jean-Laurent Riol finds the motivation for endura in ‘escape from life for a religious cause’, interprets it as a ‘mystical shortening of life’, and claims that some cases actually amounted to ritual murder (Riol 1964, 17–18).

Data

Selection criteria, unit of analysis, and validity

To ground our interpretation of endura on as much reliable evidence as possible, we collected data on all specific real-life cases we were able to find. We did not include mere mentions of endura, rather only those where someone is stated to have actually begun endura.

Our definition of endura is based on (1) the use of this term in the reports and (2) mentions of strict fasting after consolament, surpassing the regular alimentary rules for dissident ministers, who were most often called ‘Good Christians’ or just ‘Christians’. Thus, in accordance with most scholars, we excluded cases of self-harming behaviour which lacked at least one of these two evidential elements. This is why, for instance, we did not include the case of the Good Christian Auda Borelli, who is just reported to have ‘speeded up her death’ (Palès-Gobilliard 2002a, 1:480) but with no specific mention of fasting. However, we did include such cases of strict fasting related to consolament which also involved active self-harming behaviour. Like Riol (Riol 1964, 18), but unlike Borst (Borst 1953, 197, n. 22), we also included cases of hunger strike under arrest. In all four cases we encountered, the hunger striker was either a consoled Good Christian or a relation to consolament was mentioned in the source; moreover, in three out of four, the word endura was used. We did not include instances of the stereotyped derogatory motif according to which

heretics resort to the active murder of their coreligionists, either upon their request or not, to make them martyrs (e.g., Gretser 1613, 80). This polemical topos does not meet our definition either, and should be considered part of invective rather than factual description.

Our unit of observation and analysis was a case of *endura*. Therefore, if one person engaged in *endura* twice, this would constitute two observations. Given that the name of the person is almost always mentioned, usually alongside other circumstances, we can exclude the possibility that any two of the cases we discovered could actually refer to the same one. Some cases were covered by more than one mention. In these situations, we used all the descriptions to establish a synthetic view of the case; in none of them did we spot conflicting data.

While this is not the place to engage in complex debate about the reliability of records of depositions in front of the inquisition for understanding the cultures of the deponents (Ginzburg 1992; Del Col 1994; Biller 2001; Arnold 2019; Zbiral and Shaw 2022; Pihko 2024), it is important to note that we did systematically consider inquisitorial and notarial biases when reading the sources. We of course discovered some occasional negative colouring of *endura*, especially in sentencing documents, but identified no attempts of inquisitors or their notaries to manipulate the specific cases. The accounts we used were generally of good quality, comparable to the passage quoted above, and we found no reason to think that some of them would be fabrications. It is also important to say that *endura* was not a major concern of inquisitorial interrogations, and does not feature in extant interrogatories for supporters of the Good Christians from around the time *endura* was practised (Dondaine 1950, 319–20; Mollat 1926, 1:26–32); rather it was a minor aggravating circumstance in the overall involvement of suspects in heresy.

Coverage and missing data

To identify the cases, we used a combination of literature review, our own reading of relevant inquisition records in the Latin original, and keyword-based search through a corpus of digitised editions of all relevant records. Our dataset probably covers all specific cases recorded in extant sources; if we missed some, the number is likely to be in single figures. This of course does not mean at all that we have a complete dataset

of endura cases which took place, since only a fraction of inquisitorial material now survives and not all cases would have been reported.

Data collection and intercoder reliability

After identifying relevant passages, we read them in the Latin original, made decisions together on the variables we would collect and their possible values, and created a template for the dataset in a table processor (Google Sheets). Afterwards, two coders expert in Latin, the authors of this article, made independent double-blind coding. We then measured the initial intercoder agreement (for the three variables which allowed multiple choices, only complete agreement was considered for these figures). Agreement ranged from 100% to 56% depending on the variable, with a median of 89% (interquartile range 78–94%). Expectably, agreement was quite high or even complete in more straightforward variables (sex, condition, place type), and lower in the more interpretive ones (motivation, responses of the people around to endura).

We then archived the unchanged original versions of our datasets, created a table with data from both coders, and discussed all the differences one by one. During five live sessions, we achieved agreement on all values, referring back to the sources as needed, and produced the final version of the dataset.

Variables description

We collected the following data about each case:

1. *Case ID*: arbitrary unique identifier of the case.
2. *Case name*: string identifying the case, usually the name of the person.
3. *References*: source; folio; edition used; edition volume (if applicable); and page range.
4. *Geography*: location name; geographic coordinates.
5. *Sociodemographic characteristics*: sex (female, male); age group at the time of the endura (infant, child, younger, older, adult but otherwise unknown); Good Christian – full member (yes/no); family status (unmarried, married, widowed, infant or child). Sometimes general expressions concerning age allowed us to assess age group, but more often it was the familial context: we considered

those with adult children and those married more than 20 years before to be 'older'.

6. *Characterization of the practice*: diet instruction (nothing, plain water, water under conditions, sugared water, bread and water under conditions, maigre food); actual diet (same values as diet instruction); duration class (moments, days, a week or more); duration in weeks; result (death in endura, breach and survival, urgent condemnation and burning, death by suicide); resulted in death (yes/no); prayer rules mentioned (yes/no). Duration is usually based on explicit mentions, but occasionally we inferred it from the diet: if the person did not drink, we considered the duration class to be 'days' and duration in weeks to be '<1'.
7. *Health and behaviour*: condition (ill, healthy and imprisoned, healthy and free); health check of the person performed (yes/no); presence of active self-harming behaviour (yes/no).
8. *Social settings and reactions of the environment*: place type (own or family's house, other person's house, prison, hospital); the presence of caring relatives (yes/no); consolator or initiator (name of the person who suggested the endura, or 'self-inflicted' in cases without other initiators; more sets of columns to allow multiple initiators); related to the group of Petrus Auterii (yes/no); reactions of others (active support of endura, implicit consent, conflicting attitudes); was this endura the object of a conflict (yes/no/NA).
9. *Terminology*: expression (endura, no special word – diet described, killing oneself, speeding up death, serving the ill person the heretical way, weakening; more sets of columns to allow multiple values); word 'endura' used (yes/no); polemical overtones present (yes/no).
10. *Motivation and relation to consolament*: motive (desperate situation, hope for quick end, hope for salvation, hunger strike, instructions, prayer rules, sadness; more sets of columns to allow more motives under one case); relation to consolament (right after consolament, with the intention of consolament, consoled long ago, unrelated to consolament).
11. *Characterization of the testimony*: narrator's characterization (self-report, well-informed insider, well-informed outsider).

As often happens with historical sources, we could not establish the value for every instance of each variable. In such cases, we report 'unknown' in the dataset and study.

Geography, chronology, and extent

Our survey allowed us to quite precisely delimit the practice of endura in space (Fig. 1) and time, and also relate it more tightly, albeit not exclusively, to a specific heterodox milieu rather than the consolament-centred heterodox religious culture as a whole. It is well known that mentions about endura abound especially in the early-fourteenth-century registers of Geoffroy of Ablis, Bernard Gui, and Jacques Fournier (Palès-Gobilliard 1984; 2002b; Duvernoy 1965b) and predominantly map, as far as the dissidence of the ‘Good Christians’ goes, the milieu around two important figures, Petrus Auterii and his brother Guillelmus, who received their instruction in dissident religion in Italy and returned to Languedoc in late 1299 to launch an ambitious revival of dissident Christianity. Even if the focus of the three registers is known, it is still striking just how much of the data about endura is accounted for by this group. Only two cases which satisfy our criteria are not related to the Auterii group, one from 1273, the other from 1324 – in fact, at the extreme temporal bounds of the dataset. It is important to stress, nonetheless, that the 1273 case (Biller, Bruschi, and Sneddon 2011, 536–38), first pointed out by Riol (Riol 1964, 25–26), provides crystal-clear evidence of endura, and thus shows beyond doubt that the Auterii brothers had previous Languedocian examples to build upon. It is also worth noting, as Dossat remarked (Dossat 1968, 86), that in the 1273 testimony, endura seems to be something new to the inquisitor: he inquired about the reasons for this strict fasting and the record uses no specific term, while the three early-fourteenth-century registers already frame the practice as something well-known. Thus, endura must have been a recent phenomenon in Languedoc in the 1270s, probably not much older than the first mention.

Figure 1. Geographic distribution of the specific cases of endura which could be localised (N = 35). Map by Peter Ondrejka.

We did not find any specific trial evidence of endura from another important area of heterodox Christianity of the Good Christians, northcentral Italy. This is striking, because as early as 1250, in a theoretical mention which does not constitute a specific case, but otherwise is clearly linked to endura (Duvernoy 1965a, 1:235, n. 93; Thouzellier 1977, 160–61), Raniero Sacconi, Lombard inquisitor, writes: ‘Since many of them when ill have sometimes asked those who nursed them not to put any food or drink into their mouths unless the invalids could at least say the Pater noster, it is probable that many among them killed themselves this way’ (Šanjek 1974, 47; Wakefield and Evans 1991, 334). Based on this piece of evidence, we might be inclined to hypothesize that endura – as some scholars have implied – came from Italy

(Palès-Gobilliard 1984, 72; Wakefield and Evans 1991, 743, n. 15), and that its absence from Italian inquisition records is due to their lower amount of descriptive detail. We find, however, no support for Duvernoy's vast extrapolation of *endura* on 'the whole Albigensian church whose head was exiled in Sicily and whose centre was in Coni' (Duvernoy 1965a, 1:236, n. 93). While Raniero Sacconi's description clearly relates to *endura*, in terms of specific evidence we must consider *endura* a Languedocian phenomenon. The sometimes cited 1275 case from Pavia (Manselli 1980, 270; Palès-Gobilliard 1984, 72; Lambert 1998, 240, n. 40) is actually an error stemming originally from Dossat (Dossat 1948, 30), who mistook one particular mention of the normal post-consolament abstention from meat (Biller, Bruschi, and Sneddon 2011, 822) for evidence of *endura*.

The number of cases of *endura* attested in inquisition records for the period 1300–1320 was estimated at 'about twenty' (Duvernoy 1976, 167). We have been able to identify 36 specific real-life cases of *endura* which satisfied our criteria, involving 34 different persons. Among our cases, 33 are from 1300–1320. We have thus been able to extend the cases counted by Duvernoy quite considerably. In the broader context, 36 is not a low number, given the state of conservation of medieval heresy trial records, the uneven interest of inquisitors in recording details about the religious cultures they were investigating, and the deponents' probable motivation to underreport this practice. The underreporting is well exemplified by a case where a witness mentioned consolament in an earlier deposition, but only later confessed that *endura* followed (Palès-Gobilliard 1984, 190–92, 196). That the practice was probably quite well known in the dissident milieu is well illustrated by a discussion in which a mother expresses her agreement to have her ill daughter receive consolament, but only on the condition that *endura* would not be required (Palès-Gobilliard 2002a, 1:760).

While limited in time and space, and hardly a universal follow-up to consolament as was sometimes claimed (Palès-Gobilliard 1984, 72; Riol 1964, 29), and hardly stretching across a large geographic area beyond Languedoc as Duvernoy and Riol thought (Riol 1964, 37; Duvernoy 1965a, 1:236, n. 93), *endura* seems to have been a comparatively widespread practice. Already the positive evidence concerning persons connected with the 36 cases (more if we also include conversations about *endura* not constituting real cases) shows that it must have been known to at least several hundred individuals from the dissident milieu.

Outcome and duration

Among our 36 cases, we know 25 (69%) to have ended with death and 10 (28%) with survival after the person stopped fasting; in the one remaining case, the outcome is unknown. Subdividing further the 25 cases ending with death, two ended with urgent inquisitorial condemnation and burning of the person who entered endura, one with active suicide, and the remaining 22 with death in endura not involving any self-harming behaviour other than the fasting, or the interference of inquisition.

We were able to collect reasonably comprehensive data on the duration of endura, whether it ended with death or the breach of fasting. Even if the durations are potentially subject to the weaknesses of the deponents' autobiographical memory and rounding, their occasional imprecision is not likely to distort the overall picture. Something is known about the duration in 28 cases, among which, we established a duration in weeks for 25 (Fig. 2). Typically, endura lasted less than a week (18 cases, or 50%, out of which 10 ended with death), but it was not uncommon for the fasting to last a week or more (10 cases, or 28%). Endura was of very long duration in three cases, spanning 6, 7, and 12 weeks respectively, among which two concerned women and one a man; all three ended with death (Palès-Gobilliard 1984, 226, 282, 306; 2002a, 1:292).

Figure 2. Duration of endura in weeks.

Diet; concessions; endura and prayer

We observe some variation in both the prescribed and actually followed diet, and furthermore, some interesting differences between the two in cases where both are known. The prescribed diet is known for 17 cases; in seven (19% of the total 36 cases), water was allowed, in five (14%), nothing, not even water, in 4 (8%), eating of some food was allowed (Table 1). The actual diet is known for 24 cases, among which 13 (36%) allowed water, one sugared water, and one maigre food (but this endura concerned an infant and was almost immediately broken), while for the remaining 9 cases, the sources mention that the person did not even drink water (Table 2). We did not observe any gender or age group pattern in either the prescribed or actual diets.

Instruction	Count	Percent	Percent among known
plain water	7	19.4	41.1
nothing	5	13.9	29.4
bread and water under conditions	3	8.3	17.6
maigre food	1	2.8	5.9
water under conditions	1	2.8	5.9
unknown	19	52.8	-

Table 1. Overview of prescribed diet in endura cases.

Actual diet	Count	Percent	Percent among known
plain water	13	36.1	54.1
nothing	9	25	37.5
maigre food	1	2.8	4.2
sugared water	1	2.8	4.2
unknown	12	33.3	-

Table 2. Overview of actual diet in endura cases.

We also broke down the data on prescribed diet by the person who suggested endura – typically, but not always, the Good Christian or Christians who conferred the consolament (Table 3). We observe one pattern quite clearly: Petrus and Guillelmus Auterii, brothers and the central figures of the revival of heterodox Christianity around 1300 in Languedoc, were the initiators of most enduras. We also see that all known concessions to eat something were made by less central figures. The two brothers can thus be counted among endura hardliners (Molinier 1881, 289).

Initiator	Bread and water with conditions	Nothing	Plain water	Water with conditions	Maigre food	Unknown	Total
Petrus Auterii	0	0	2	0	0	8	10
Guillelmus Auterii	0	2	1	1	0	4	8
Pradas Tavernerii	1	1	1	1	1	1	6
self-inflicted	0	1	2	0	0	3	6
unknown	0	0	1	0	0	4	5
Petrus Sancii	1	1	0	0	0	0	2
Bernardus Audoyni	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
Bernardus Clerici	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
Bernardus Tilhol	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
Guillelmus Prunelli	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
Philippus de Talayracho	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
Ramundus Beloti	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
Ramundus Petri	0	0	0	0	1	0	1

Table 3. Prescribed diet by initiator of endura. The figures do not add up to 36, because some cases involved more initiators.

Our examination of the data partly challenges the mainstream line of interpretation of the endura diet, which sees it as very closely tied to the normal fasting requirements for Good Christians, also documented for novices preparing to receive consolament (Palès-Gobilliard 2002a, 1:500, 518, 528, 656; 2002c, 2:1478). This interpretation, that we might call ‘apologetic’ for simplicity, was first proposed by Borst, who claimed that the word endura ‘initially referred to a preparatory fasting period undertaken by novices’ (Borst 1953, 197), a claim that he never backed up by any source; in fact, neither we nor authors of the literature we reviewed know of any example of such use of the word. For Borst, endura was then a variant of the fasting destined for those who could not undergo the normal preparatory fasting, such as the

dying and children (Borst 1953, 197). Duvernoy and Brenon developed this idea further. For Duvernoy, the Good Christians conferring consolament would have certainly liked to remain for several days or even weeks, guiding the person through preparatory fasting and instructing them on prayer, but in the conditions of inquisitorial persecution and terminal illness, this was rarely possible (Duvernoy 1976, 169). Finally, Brenon claims that *endura* as we know it is ‘probably a misinterpretation of a period of ritual fasting on bread and water, observed, in accordance with the rule, by the newly ordained members’ (Brenon 2000, 82). According to her, *endura* originates in probationary, preparatory fasting, with the expectation that if the person who had received consolament survived, they could continue living the normal life of a Good Christian (Brenon 1992, 330–31).

There is certainly some substance to seeing the origin of *endura* in preparatory fasting, and considering it a condensed form of such fasting. Traces of this can be observed in five cases – in addition to Raniero Sacconi’s aforementioned theoretical text from 1250 (Šanjek 1974, 47) – of concession concerning eating or drinking as long as proper prayer rules are observed, a connection that scholars writing about *endura* have not failed to notice (Riol 1964, 27; Moore 1994, 33). In the earliest known specific case, Rixendis of Miraval, a person from the household of a certain lady Fays, reported that after receiving her consolament, the lady did not eat any more and drank only water. When the inquisitor asked why, Rixendis answered that Fays ‘neither knew the prayer according to the manner of the heretics, nor was there anyone who could tell her it’ (Biller, Bruschi, and Sneddon 2011, 538–39). Looking beyond *endura*-related evidence, the idea that the recently consoled might wish for assistance in preprandial prayer might help explain a testimony, predating the Auterii revival, concerning a person who, after receiving consolament, waited with his meals until he had the company of Good Christians (Biller, Bruschi, and Sneddon 2011, 696–98). The reason Rixendis gave can hardly be considered her speculation, since there are further cases, from the Auterii milieu this time, where the opportunity is offered to mitigate *endura* if prayer had been recited. For instance, Petrus Sicredi was told ‘not to eat, unless he can say Our Father’, even if he in the end did not use this opportunity and only drank water (Palès-Gobilliard 2002a, 1:608–10). Ramundus Garsendi was allowed only to drink water and only after reciting Our Father, even if he in fact consumed nothing (Palès-Gobilliard 1984, 196).

Such examples could help explain the original nucleus of endura. Nevertheless, the 'apologetic' line of interpretation, which tries to draw endura as close to normal Good Christian fasting and as distant from assisted suicide as possible, remains incomplete at best. Firstly, the endura diet is radically different from both the normal alimentary rules observed by the Good Christians and their rules for fasting days. The normal alimentary rules involved permanent avoidance of meat, dairy, and other animal products apart from fish and crayfish (Dondaine 1950, 315; Šanjek 1974, 43; Mollat 1926, 1:18; Palès-Gobilliard 1984, 214), but did not require the avoidance of, for instance, bread or vegetables. Among endura cases, however, we found only four cases where any allowance for food was made. Concerning fasting periods, an authoritative source on the matter informs us that fasting was obligatory every Monday, Wednesday, and Friday, when the Good Christians also avoided fish, crayfish, wine, and oil. In addition, they observed three yearly fasting periods of approximately forty days, including a couple of stricter weeks, when they avoided not only fish, crayfish, wine and oil, but even vegetables (Dondaine 1950, 315). Not even rules for the strictest fasting days thus account for the strictness of endura. If anything, the endura diet resembles only strict fasting held by some Good Christians after the death of somebody they consoled (Duvernoy 1965c, 2:29, 39), and fasting as punishment after they had touched a person of the opposite sex, where three days of fasting without even drinking is reported (Duvernoy 1965c, 2:31). Secondly, if we wanted to maintain that endura was 'condensed' fasting, in the sense of a rule of life of the Good Christians intensified in the special case of a deathbed consolamentum in order to make doubly sure about salvation, we would have hard time explaining why no other among the numerous rules of life of the Good Christians, such as prayer, contact with persons of the other sex, and the like, ever obtained, as far as evidence goes, such a 'condensed' form, but rather remained at the exact level normally required from any Good Christian. Thirdly, prayer rules are absent from too many detailed accounts of specific conversations about endura to let us conclude that they were being systematically mentioned by those who suggested endura and were just left unrecorded, while many other fine details were retained. If so much depended on prayer rules and there was an easy legitimate way to feed the person, we could hardly explain why many questions on dissident prayer were not asked, and summarized in the depositions. Finally, there is positive evidence of instructions after consolament which only rely upon the normal alimentary rules of the Good Christians

(Palès-Gobilliard 2002a, 1:890), seemingly considered sufficient for achieving salvation.

A much more credible explanation of both the complete silence on prayer in 31 cases and the strictness of the practice is that *endura* was a bespoke practice in which the Good Christians themselves – rather than some followers hypothetically misunderstanding the Good Christians’ actual instructions, as Brenon seems to suggest – often stripped the complex rules around prayer and eating down to a simple and practical, if stern, precept which could be summarized as follows: you have received consolament, so fast strictly, make sure you do not sin any more and die in this state, and you will be saved. While occasionally and unsystematically concessions were made and conditioned by following the proper prayer rules, this option was not offered to all or even most. If prayer rules and the idea of ‘condensing’ preparatory fasting into a shorter period by making it stricter may have historically been at the origin of *endura*, it had nevertheless become a form of fasting of its own by the first decade of the fourteenth century, from where most of the evidence comes. While killing the person assuming it does not appear to have been the explicit purpose behind *endura*, the fact that it went much beyond the normal fasting requirements made death a rather likely outcome and, at least in the case of people who seemed seriously ill, a perhaps not unwelcome one.

Some authors have tried to explain the harshness of *endura*, hypothetically augmented from simple fasting and concerns to precisely follow prayer rules, by the historical context of the growing pressure of inquisitorial investigations and, consequently, the increasing risk of not being able, next time, to get a Good Christian who could confer consolament, should *endura* be broken and should the state of salvation ensured by consolament be lost (Duvernoy 1976, 168–69; Brenon 1992, 331; Lambert 1998, 241–42). This contextual interpretation can be considered the current mainstream, and a crucial component of the ‘apologetic’ line of interpretation of *endura*. In order to assess this claim, we took the year of 1308 as a turning point, since it is in 1308 that the inquisitorial campaigns of Geoffroy of Ablis and Bernard Gui covered by the extant registers began (Palès-Gobilliard 1984; 2002b), which we know exerted big pressure on the Auterii milieu, including the arrest and execution of most of the full members. Comparing only cases dated with a high degree of certainty to 1300–1307 (10 cases) vs. 1308 or later (8 cases), we found no evidence of such a relation: if we observe any pattern, then it is in fact the three-times-higher incidence

of consuming nothing at all in both the prescribed and actually observed diets in 1300 to 1307 in comparison to 1308 or later (Table 4). Our numbers are of course small here for firm conclusions, but at the very least, we can say that the idea of the increasing strictness of the endura diet under tighter repression finds no corroboration in our data.

Diet	Count: instruction 1300 to 1307	Count: instruction 1308 or later	Count: actual diet 1300 to 1307	Count: actual diet 1308 or later
bread and water under conditions	1	1	0	0
nothing	3	1	6	2
plain water	1	2	2	3
water under conditions	1	0	0	0
unknown	4	4	2	3

Table 4. Prescribed and observed endura diets: cases from 1300–1307 vs. cases from 1308 or later. Only the 18 cases which can be dated with high certainty are included.

As a final point on diet, we can observe an interesting gap between the diet prescribed and that actually followed. We know both in 17 cases. In 12, the practice is the same as the instruction, but in the remaining five, it departs from it, and surprisingly, in all these cases, the practice was actually stricter than the instruction. In three, both bread and water were allowed under certain conditions, but either water alone or nothing was consumed (Biller, Bruschi, and Sneddon 2011, 538; Palès-Gobilliard 2002a, 1:608, 610, 738; Duvernoy 1965a, 1:490, 494–95, 500–501, 504). In two, only water was allowed, but the person undertaking endura consumed nothing (Palès-Gobilliard 1984, 196; 2002a, 1:722). If the decision was taken not to follow the instructions, the endura was already dropped altogether rather than mitigated. Of course, we cannot know how much these instances of practice stricter than the instruction were motivated by the health of the ill, often dying person, for whom it might have been more painful to eat or drink than to abstain, and how much by the intent to make doubly sure not to lose the state of salvation. Nevertheless this gap between prescription and practice, going exclusively in the direction of more strictness in practice, defies expectation and has not been remarked upon before.

Gender, age group, and family status

An important set of questions concern patterns in the sociodemographic characteristics of those who entered endura. Beginning with gender, women seem more represented than men, constituting 21 cases (58%) while men the remaining 15 (42%), but the difference is not large. Evidence on endura thus does not mirror starving to death in Jainism (*sallekhanā*), where women clearly prevail (Braun 2008, 922). On the other hand, should we compare these figures with those given by Murray in his comprehensive quantitative study of suicide in medieval Europe, women turn out to be more represented in enduras than in suicides, where they constitute only ca. 26% of known cases (Murray 1998, 1:380–81; cf. Schmitt 1976, 5).

We cannot establish the specific age of persons entering endura, because Languedocian inquisitors rarely recorded it, but we can classify some of them into broader age groups. We encounter two infants among our cases; in one, the endura was kept and the girl died (Palès-Gobilliard 2002a, 1:584), in the other, the mother decided to ignore the instructions and breastfed her daughter, who then lived for another year (Duvernoy 1965c, 2:414–15). In theory, infants and children were not supposed to be offered consolament, but in actual practice they sometimes were, even if there is evidence of doubts of a confessor over whether it should be done (Duvernoy 1965c, 2:17) and of disapproval from some members of the Auterii group (Duvernoy 1965d, 3:144, 221). Notwithstanding, even the leader of the group himself, Petrus Auterii, conferred consolament to a boy of two when the boy's grandmother urged him to do so; in that case, he did not recommend endura, he only made sure with the mother that the boy would be given no food normally prohibited to Good Christians (Palès-Gobilliard 2002a, 1:890).

For 17 cases (47%), we know that the person was older (in our division, forty or more), while only 4 cases (11%) are known to have been younger adults (less than forty; Table 5). However, in 13 cases (36%), it is not possible to establish age beyond saying that they were adults: these cases may also contain a good number of younger people, since kinship-related proxies (e.g. existence of adult children) make it easier to infer the age of older individuals. We should thus not assume from our data that endura was only rarely recommended to younger adults.

Family status is known in 29 cases. In 12 (33%), those entering endura were married; in 9 (25%), they were widowed; in 6 (17%), they were unmarried; in 2 (6%), as already mentioned, they were infants (Table 5). Somewhat against our intuitions, we thus find no evidence of special attraction to endura among widows and widowers. Our findings might be cautiously compared to Murray’s on suicide in legal documents from England, where married people were also preponderant, constituting three quarters of the cases where family status is known (Murray 1998, 1:398). An interesting case is that of Guillelma, wife of Martinus de Prouado, who entered endura and specifically asked her friend Alazaytz to marry her husband after her death, which is what happened (Palès-Gobilliard 2002a, 1:460).

Gender	Age group	Family status	Count	Percent	
female	older	widowed	8	22.2	
		unknown	1	2.8	
		married	1	2.8	
	older Total			10	27.8
	adult but otherwise unknown	married	3	8.3	
		unknown	2	5.6	
		widowed	1	2.8	
		unmarried	1	2.8	
	adult but otherwise unknown Total			7	19.4
	younger	married	2	5.6	
	younger Total			2	5.6
infant	infant or child	2	5.6		
infant Total			2	5.6	
female Total			21	58.3	
male	older	unmarried	3	8.3	
		married	3	8.3	
		unknown	1	2.8	
	older Total			7	19.4
	adult but otherwise unknown	unknown	3	8.3	
		married	3	8.3	
	adult but otherwise unknown Total			6	16.7
	younger	unmarried	2	5.6	
younger Total			2	5.6	
male Total			15	41.7	
Grand Total			36	100.0	

Table 5. Sociodemographic characteristics: gender, age group, and family status.

In three cases (involving two people, Amiel de Perlis and Guillelmus Belibasta), the person entering endura was a Good Christian, already living for a longer time under the rules for full members. In all other cases, they were lay supporters.

Health; endura and self-harming behaviour

There is no denying that endura typically involved ill persons. Among the 31 cases where the person's health state can be established from the sources, in 25 they were ill (69% among our 36 cases), and sources often make explicit that the illness seemed serious. For instance, when Galharda Scaunerii fell ill, 'it was commonly believed that she would shortly die' (Duvernoy 1965c, 2:13–14). Three cases involved ascertaining the health state of the patient (Palès-Gobilliard 1984, 190; Duvernoy 1965a, 1:494, 500, 503; 1965d, 3:362): elsewhere indeed, there are cases where even the consolament of the sick itself was denied to somebody who did not yet seem to be dying (Duvernoy 1976, 168). However, it would clearly be too much to conclude from these mentions that health checks were performed in any systematic way, and thus to support the more apologetic line of interpretation by saying that endura was only recommended to people after making sure their recovery seemed unlikely.

Even more clearly, the interpretation of endura as a practice for just the moribund fails to account for six cases (17%) which involved healthy persons, even if there is evidence of other forms of distress in 5 of them (4 were under arrest, 1 in depression due to a bad decision concerning his lover). Only in one case, albeit widely cited in literature, was endura combined with more active forms of self-harming behaviour, involving poisoning, swallowing glass shards, bleeding, and laying down on a cold floor (Palès-Gobilliard 2002a, 1:310, 456–60, 480–82, 546–48); this person, Guillelma, wife of Martinus de Prouado, was also suffering from illness. In another case, a woman was 'weakening herself' in an unspecified way during her endura (Palès-Gobilliard 2002a, 1:546). In the remaining 34 cases, active suicide or active self-harming behaviour is not attested as part of endura. However negatively the Good Christians viewed the world, they generally avoided killing just like mainstream Christians or more, extending the prohibition of killing even to most animals (Duvernoy 1965a, 1:378, 383; 1965c, 2:12).

Social settings, reactions of the environment, and conflict

We find four kinds of social settings where people underwent endura: their own home or their family's home (21; 58%), another person's home (8; 22%), prison (4; 11%); and hospital (2; 6%). In the one remaining case, the type of place is unknown. One's own home is the natural place to be; more of interest are the eight cases which take place in another person's house. Interestingly, six among them involve women. Sometimes this circumstance is related to their choices, which might have been motivated by religion as much as by personal situation; for instance, two women fled from their homes, one of them specifically from her husband, and entered endura in other people's houses (Palès-Gobilliard 1984, 226; 2002a, 1:660).

Whether in one's own or another person's home, we find the persons in endura mostly surrounded by those close to them (24 cases, or 67%). Only in the four prison cases (11%) do we know such company to have been lacking. In the remaining 8 (22%), we do not know who else was present.

Observing the reactions of those who were present, we found 5 cases (14%) in which the people around showed active support for the endura; 18 cases (50%) in which their implicit consent can be assumed (that is, we found the observance of endura by those around, but no evidence of either explicit support or disapproval); and in 6 cases (17%), we observed some sort of conflict around endura. For the remaining 7 (19%), the reactions are either unknown or the variable does not apply because the persons were isolated from their community through imprisonment.

Different kinds of conflict are attested. In four cases, the person who undertook endura got better and requested food against the wishes of their caretakers (Palès-Gobilliard 2002a, 1:414, 720–22; Duvernoy 1965c, 2:15–16, 413–14; 1965d, 3:143, 264–66). (The figures do not add up to 6, because some cases involved more types of conflict.) The most detailed account is that of the endura of Galharda Scaunerii: according to the testimony of her son, 'after five or six days that she only drank cold water, she got somewhat better and started to ask for food, but her daughter Marquesia did not want to give her anything but water, following the precept of the heretic', after which the old woman 'scolded her daughter for not giving her food' (Duvernoy 1965c, 2:15–16). She then started eating, vegetables at first, later even meat (Duvernoy 1965c, 2:414–15). In two cases, a companion or caretaker

wanted them to eat but they intended to keep the endura (Duvernoy 1965a, 1:388; Palès-Gobilliard 2002a, 1:738). In four cases, conflict broke out between different persons around, such as in the case of Petrus Sicredi, whose children wanted to follow their father's dissident convictions, while his brother was displeased (Palès-Gobilliard 2002a, 1:608, 610, 738). In such cases, endura could sometimes end very quickly, as in the case of Iacoba Petri, an infant who was breastfed by her mother immediately after the dissident minister and her husband – more keen on the religion of the Good Christians than herself and concerned to make their ill daughter into 'an angel of God' – left the house (Duvernoy 1965c, 2:414–15).

It is clear that endura tested the conviction of the believers, and raised mixed reactions, first observed by Le Roy Ladurie in his now classical work of historical anthropology, which also highlighted how interesting for anthropology some inquisition records are (Le Roy Ladurie 1982, 342–43). Even those otherwise positively disposed towards the Good Christians often explicitly challenged or rejected the practice (Duvernoy 1965a, 1:284, 497–98, 499; 1965c, 2:459, 484). Indeed, it could even dissuade those who liked the general idea from undergoing consolament altogether (Duvernoy 1965a, 1:504).

Terminology

Since our sources are criminal trial records, it is not without interest that only in five cases does a negative evaluation of endura transpire from the terminology used by the notary, such as 'you are inflicting death upon yourself' (Palès-Gobilliard 2002a, 1:848). Negative connotations such as killing oneself (3 cases; 8%) and speeding up one's death (3 cases; 8%) appear more often in records of sentences than in deposition records.

Much more widespread than such negative connotations is the use of the quite neutral term 'endura', meaning simply 'fasting'. It is used to describe the practice in 20 cases (56%). In another 14 (39%), only the diet is described, without any special name: for instance, 'the heretic (...) ordered that he does not eat or drink any more, which was done' (Duvernoy 1965a, 1:401). In another two cases, we find expressions about serving the ill person 'in the manner of the heretics' (Palès-Gobilliard 2002a, 1:722) or 'as the heretic said' (Palès-Gobilliard 2002a, 1:414). (The figures in this section do

not add up to 36, or 100%, because more expression types were sometimes used in relation to the same case.)

Motivation

Finally, we were interested in the stated motivation for undertaking endura, a crucial component for its overall interpretation. By motivation, we do not mean so much the internal and individual attitude, very rarely reported in the sources, but, rather, the complicated and socially embedded factors which contributed to the choice, and which were not always under the complete control of those entering endura. Sometimes the persons entering endura had more agency, as the iron determination of some to really not eat (Duvernoy 1965a, 1:388; Palès-Gobilliard 2002a, 1:716–18) makes clear. But sometimes they seem guided by those around them, and sometimes, finally, they did not partake in the decision, as is most clearly the case with the two baby girls.

Scholars writing about endura have strongly emphasised motivation by belief, specifically the hope for salvation after the reception of consolament (Guiraud 1935, 1:82; Borst 1953, 197; Riol 1964, 21; Duvernoy 1976, 164; Brenon 1992, 331). Nothing in the data we collected directly opposes hope for salvation as a valid baseline interpretation of the motivation for endura. The perspective of salvation or ‘good death’, in the sense of death in a state of salvation achieved by consolament, is indeed strongly expressed in several accounts (Duvernoy 1965a, 1:494, 501, 504; 1965d, 3:143). This belief could sometimes become so strong that it was even reported to have changed feelings and behaviours: a witness reports that she ‘was present at [her mother-in-law’s] burial and wept over her, but with her eyes remaining dry, since she knew that she [her mother-in-law] was hereticated when still alive’ (Duvernoy 1965a, 1:490). However, the image of the motivation to start endura that our data offer is more diverse.

Hope for salvation is well established as a motivation: it is clearly stated in 8 cases (22%), and we should not interpret from silence that it was absent from the others. Clearly, taking the high risk associated with receiving consolament, and endura with it, makes little sense without the eschatological hopes connected to it. Nevertheless, we must pay attention to mentions of other motivations, too: in four cases (11%),

endura was in the form of a hunger strike by people under arrest; in four cases (11%) – three of the hunger strikes and an additional one – we observed that a desperate situation played its part; in two (6%), hope for a quick end is mentioned; in one (3%), the concern to keep prayer rules, and in another (3%), sadness (Table 6; the counts do not add up to 36, or 100%, because more than one motivation can be traced in some cases). Even more prominently, as many as 15 cases explicitly mention instructions, usually by the Good Christians who conferred consolament, as a motive for endura. For instance, Na Roqua would not get any food or drink, ‘because it must not be done’ (Duvernoy 1965a, 1:388). Guillelma, wife of Vitalis Gilaberti, whose infant daughter received consolament, deposed that her mother-in-law ‘prevented her (...) from breastfeeding her daughter’, who then died (Palès-Gobilliard 2002a, 1:584). Such social pressure is most explicit in the case of Galharda Scaunerii, who confided to her friend Sybilina Petri that ‘she would eat most gladly, but she does not dare to tell the believers because of shame and fear that they do not despise her should she eat after she had been received’ (Duvernoy 1965a, 1:414) – concerns that in the end, Sybilina helped Galharda to overcome. Here, as is often the case with enduras which became objects of discontent, the motivation for undertaking endura appears not to have derived from a highly internalized personal attitude, but from various highly socially entangled factors.

Motivation	Count	Percent
instructions	15	41.7
hope for salvation	8	22.2
desperate situation	4	11.1
hunger strike	4	11.1
hope for quick end	2	5.6
prayer rules	1	2.8
sadness	1	2.8
unknown	13	36.1

Table 6. Motivations for endura. The counts do not add up to 36 (or 100%), because more than one motivation can be traced in some cases; rather, they show the proportion of cases in which a given motivation can be established.

In addition, when we speak about motivation by hope for salvation, we must ask whose hope. Hope for salvation of the person in endura is, in fact, much more often voiced by relatives or acquaintances (Duvernoy 1965a, 1:501; 1965d, 3:143) than the person him or herself. This again underlines the influence of social norms, rather than

the individual psychology and decision-making of the person undertaking endura alone. After all, we usually encounter endura as suggested either by the dissident ministers who conferred the consolament or by some fervent supporter rather than as something those persons themselves suggested or even inquired about.

Hope for salvation thus hardly tells the full story. This conclusion is further underlined by cases which do not show the typical relation to consolament, believed to grant salvation (Table 7). In 29 cases (81%), endura indeed features, as expected, as an immediate follow-up to consolament. But in a further three cases (8%), long-initiated Good Christians enter endura as a sort of hunger strike rather than to make doubly sure of salvation. Even more intriguing, however, are three cases where endura involves persons who had not received consolament at all. One is the case of Limosus Negri (Duvernoy 2003, 111), which is completely unrelated to consolament: constituting a case apart, Limosus visibly found inspiration in, but was not part of, the Good Christians' milieu. The other two cases, those of Petrus Ramundi de Hugonibus and an unnamed woman (Palès-Gobilliard 2002a, 1:546, 848), depart completely from the usual pattern: they undertake endura with the wish of hopefully receiving consolament, but endura is not at all a follow-up to the rite, and consolament in fact does not, and in one case cannot possibly take place because of the particular circumstances. This use of endura seriously defies the widespread 'rational-choice theory' notion, explicit (Molinier 1881, 284; Guiraud 1935, 1:82) or implicit (Riol 1964, 21; Duvernoy 1976, 164), that endura was an outcome of a rational consideration of costs and benefits, in this case, salvation, since no concept of salvation we know of from the milieu of the Good Christians allows salvation without consolament. Should endura lead to death, it could, in such cases, result in the person being damned for all eternity rather than saved according to all beliefs we know from this milieu. Thus, we should probably search for the explanation of such cases in the difficult situations the persons were in (prison in one case, evidence of self-harming behaviour in another, making a difficult situation or depression likely), rather than in eschatology, which dovetails well with the finding that self-harming behaviour is often chosen by the resourceless (Grojean 2022). Endura had various uses, and similarly diverse were the motivations to undertake it.

Relation to consolament	Count	Percent
right after consolament	29	80.6
consoled long ago	3	8.3
with the intention of consolament	2	5.6
unrelated to consolament	1	2.8
unknown	1	2.8

Table 7. Relation of endura cases to consolament.

While we would not like to underestimate the role of beliefs in motivating behaviour, we feel that yet another widespread notion needs revising: the idea that endura was motivated by dualism, defined here as the belief that the world was made and is governed by evil forces (Guiraud 1935, 1:80; Manselli 1980, 197, 270; Tsiamis, Tounta, and Poulakou-Rebelakou 2016, 179). Dualism is, in itself, well established in the religious culture of the Good Christians, with substantial evidence coming even from inquisitorial records (Taylor 2013). However, it is quite a leap to claim that dualism was a motivation for endura. This stems, in fact, more from speculation over the normative theology of the Good Christians than from the interpretation of any actual testimonies: we found no evidence whatsoever among our cases for this association with ideas about the evil nature or origin of the world in any of the real-life cases we surveyed, and unlike the motivation of endura by a general hope for salvation, we tend to discard its supposed motivation by dualism.

Conclusion

Our systematic quantitative survey of all known real-life cases of endura allows us to conclude that most interpretations of endura proposed so far were not entirely wrong, but were often one-sided or incomplete. First and foremost, most prescribed and actually practised variants of the endura diet were far too strict and far too different from the normal rules for even the strictest fasting periods kept by the Good Christians to represent a simple condensation of the normal rules of their religious life. The contrast is especially strong in cases where endura was not suggested and only the normal rules of avoiding animal products were communicated after the consolament (Palès-Gobilliard 2002a, 1:890). Endura was also certainly sometimes

associated with prayer rules that allowed the prescribed diet to be somewhat mitigated, but this is not the full story either: we can hardly believe that the important details of the conditions under which eating and drinking was normally possible would simply have been omitted from most of the mentions and reported conversations. Rather, the Good Christians actually simplified endura to its backbone – to a form of fasting more radical than even the diet for the strictest of their fasting days, and one whose possible and not entirely unwelcome outcome was death. Only occasionally and unsystematically did they offer the option of mitigating this harsh fasting as long as the proper prayers were recited. Furthermore, even those who were told about such mitigation seem to have preferred dying in peace to using this opportunity. Thus, just like the ‘dark legend’ of endura as religious suicide – at times even religious murder – finds little justification in the sources, also the ‘apologetic’ line of interpretation fails to account for many details in the evidence we reviewed in this article. Yes, endura might have theoretically been meant for those who made the choice themselves, but in practice, two cases involved infants, and many others bear witness of social pressure and limited agency. Yes, endura may have been destined for the seriously ill – in fact, for those that were dying –, but we can hardly ignore the evidence of healthy persons undertaking it or of two women on the run who sought, in endura, a solution to their situation. Yes, endura may have been driven by eschatological hopes, but too many cases mention, alongside or instead of such hopes, the authority of the Good Christians and pressure from those around to consider eschatological beliefs the only motivation. Yes, endura cannot be simply subsumed under assisted suicide, but sometimes it was put to use with the purpose of shortening one’s life, and such cases, even those which did not involve any other self-harming behaviour, meet at least a minimal definition of suicide. Yes, endura may have developed towards its strict form under the pressure of inquisitorial investigations, but comparing cases before and after the start of the big investigations of the Auterii milieu, we found nothing to corroborate the claim that more acute pressure corresponded to harsher forms of the endura diet.

In final judgement, the extant evidence about endura is fundamentally ambiguous, and, as such, it defies any attempt at an unambiguous overarching interpretation, whether accusatory or apologetic, and whether stressing external conditions or internal psychological factors. Endura was one of those institutions in the making which are characterized by astonishing plasticity: sometimes it was taken for granted

and followed just like that, often without a special name; sometimes the ideas around *endura* crystallized into a more coherent theology. A systematic survey of the data allowed us to reaffirm this ambiguity, which ultimately constitutes an interpretive strength: it allows for all the variation we were able to quantitatively express and qualitatively exemplify in how medieval supporters of the dissidence of the Good Christians practised it, how they understood it, and how they responded to it. We should probably know by now that cultural practices almost always gain such ambiguity if they are put to use by many different practitioners and in many different situations, and that they are subject to constant reinterpretation and remoulding, which changes even the way humans 'live' them, and by that, what these practices really are. But apparently, it never hurts to be reminded of this irreducible ambiguity of all things human, or at least all the interesting ones.

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Data availability statement

The data used in this study is available in the form of a tabulator-separated values file (TSV) in the Figshare repository at:

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